

Water depth (cm)

Water depth during the crop-growth period at the Chinsurah Rice Research Station, West Bengal, India, 1978.

Yield, grain characteristics, and field tolerance for stem borers of some wetland rice cultures. Chinsurah, India.

Variety	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)	Grain wt loss (%) due to husk removal	Estimated kernel yield (t/ha)	100-grain wt (g)		Stem borer damage ^b
				Rough rice	Head rice	
Kumargore	3.6	21	2.8	3.2	2.5	1
OC1393	3.0	20	2.4	3.0	2.4	3
NC1281	2.5	27	1.8	2.4	1.8	3
Patnai 23	2.5	18	2.1	3.0	2.5	3
CNM539	2.5	27	1.8	1.8	1.3	3
CN603	2.5	13	2.1	3.1	2.7	3
Pankaj (check)	1.0	19	0.8	2.5	2.0	5
C.D. (5%)	1.0		0.7			

^a Mean of 3 replications. ^b At 40 days after transplanting; 1 = resistant, 3 = moderately resistant, 5 = moderately susceptible, 7 = susceptible, and 9 = highly susceptible.

indica. Although the bold-grained Kumargore had a high rough rice yield, its kernel yield after husk removal was reduced to 2.8 t/ha. Based on kernel yield, Kumargore was statistically similar to OC1393 and CN603, and superior to other entries.

CN603 is of intermediate height with more culm stiffness than most tall indicas.

It has long slender grains with white kernels. Most traditional indica cultivars in West Bengal have bold, red kernels.

In addition to flood submergence and water stagnation the trial was subjected to severe stem borer incidence at early tillering. Kumargore was tolerant of stem borers; CN603 and CNM539 were moderately tolerant. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Cold tolerance

Selection for cold tolerance at seedling stage during rapid generation advance

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During the rapid generation advance (RGA) of breeding materials for low temperature areas, screening for cold

tolerance at different growth stages may be desirable. The easiest stage to screen is at seedling stage when bulk materials can be easily handled and very little space is needed. The possibility of screening for cold tolerance at the seedling stage during RGA was tested. A preliminary trial used a susceptible cultivar, IR8 (a semidwarf indica), and a cold-tolerant

cultivar, Fujisaka 5 (a japonica). Screening for cold water tolerance at the seedling stage involved germinating the seeds in pots and subjecting the 10-day-old seedlings to 12°C water for 10 days, IR8 turned brown, but Fujisaka 5 remained green. However, such treatment delayed flowering by 7 days in Fujisaka 5 and by as much as 22 days in IR8 (Table 1), and partially defeated the purpose of the RGA in shortening the life cycle, especially in IR8.

The possibility of screening for cold tolerance at the seedling stage of segregating F₃, materials with a consequent delay in heading date was studied using the crosses IR20654 (K78-13/IR5908-125-1) and IR22553 (Fujisaka 5/Kn1B-361-1-8-6-9).

The seeds were sown in plastic pots (46 x 46 mm top, 36 x 36 mm bottom) filled with soil and added fertilizer. Ten days after sowing, the plants were subjected to 12°C cold water for 10 days. The plants were scored for leaf yellowing: a score of 1 was best, and 9 indicated almost dead or dead plants. Each F₃ line had a corresponding untreated plant, which was grown to maturity, and the flowering dates of both sets were noted.

A number of F₃ plants (4% in IR22553 and 14% in IR20654) had scores of 1 to 3. Removal of the susceptible lines (score 7 to 9) eliminated 87 and 58% of the F₃, plants in the two crosses studied and increased the available greenhouse space for use within 30 days after sowing.

The results show that cold water treatment at the seedling stage generally delayed the heading date of the two

Table 1. Growth duration of 2 rice varieties subjected to low water temperature at seedling stage. IRRI, 1980.

Variety	Growth (days)		Cold tolerance score ^a
	Treated plants	Untreated plants	
Fujisaka 5	52*	45	1.2
IR8	102*	80	7.7

*Significant at .05 level. ^a Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale of 1-9: 1 = Plants have natural color and normal rate of growth and flowering. 9 = Plants stunted with yellow to brown leaves and much delayed in development and poor panicle exertion.

Table 2. Effect of a 10-day 12°C water treatment 10 days after sowing on the growth duration of 2 rice varieties. IRRI, 1980.

Observation	IR22553		IR20654	
	Plants (no.)	% of the population	Plants (no.)	% of the population
Delayed flowering	203	46	362	38
Same flowering duration	103	23	307	32
Early flowering	73	17	137	14
Dead	63	14	148	16
Total number tested	442		954	

crosses studied (Table 2). Some lines, however, actually headed earlier as a result of the treatment. Since the plants are still segregating, it is not possible to definitely say that the treatment caused earliness or delay in heading.

In general, the plants damaged severely

by the cold water treatment showed a greater delay in heading (Table 3). In both crosses, the difference in average flowering date between the treated plants and the control is small for plants with a score of 1 to 3. Screening for cold tolerance at the seedling stage can be

Table 3. Effect of 10-day 12°C water treatment 10 days after sowing on the yellowing of leaves of 2 rice varieties. IRRI, 1980.

Score	F ₃ plants ^a (no.)	
	IR22553	IR20654
1-3	17 (+5)	129 (+3)
Green		
5	39 (+5)	261 (+9)
Light green		
7-9	386 (+6)	564 (+8)
Yellow - dead		
Total	442	954

^aFigures inside the parentheses show the average number of days heading was delayed.

conducted during the RGA of F₃ plants without any great delay in heading of the tolerant lines. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Yellow wilt of rice in the lower Amazon Basin, Brazil

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The yellow wilt problem of rice was noted in a few mechanically cultivated fields of irrigated rice in the lower Amazon Basin in the second crop season of 1978. The disorder became more serious in the first and second crop seasons of 1979 on IR22 in the varzea marshland soils.

The rice plant's growth usually proceeded normally until 1 or 2 weeks before the flowering-milk stages; then the older leaves began to die rapidly and the younger leaves turned yellow brown and gradually died back from the tips. About 1 or 2 weeks before harvest, the yellow-brown leaves suddenly withered. Ripening was accelerated and at harvest the affected plants looked dehydrated, dirty, weak, and droopy; and had no green or light-yellow leaves.

Such crops had many decayed and dead roots and were usually attacked by *Helminthosporium* leaf spot, *Cercospora* leaf spot, *Pyricularia* neck blast, or *Rhizoctonia* sheath blight, or two or more of the diseases. But such attacks appeared secondary. Yields were low

because of the low photosynthetic activity of the leaves and the poor root systems. The appropriate harvest time was difficult to determine because the leaves dried and died before maturation, and the same panicles contained green as well as ripe grains. Grain quality was usually poor. In cases where the disorder occurred before flowering, plant growth was poor. A yellow-brown discoloration appeared on the tips of green leaves, and the older leaves dried and died, starting from the tips. At flowering the panicles varied in height and few leaves remained green. Leaves then withered more rapidly. Drainage for harvesting accelerated the withering. The symptoms usually occurred on plants grown in soils of low organic matter. The name *yellow wilt* was used because of the yellowing and wilting symptoms.

A combination of factors including iron toxicity, potassium deficiency, and disease incidence was suspected to cause yellow wilt. Recent studies show that the yellow wilt disorder is associated with potassium deficiency in the soil solution and low potassium content of the plants.

Increasing the supply of potassium fertilizer from the previous recommendation of 20-30 kg/ha to 70-90 kg/ha and

split application of potassium noticeably alleviated the disorder.

Three tentative remedies have been recommended:

1. submergence of the varzea marshland soils for at least 1 month before planting;
2. increase in potassium fertilizer up to 70-90 kg/ha and splitting its application; and
3. application of higher levels of potassium fertilizer, but avoidance of excessive nitrogen dressing, at about the maximum-tillering stage. ■

Experimental observations on rice sheath rot disease

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Semidwarf rice cultivars are often susceptible to sheath rot disease caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae*, but tall cultivars are relatively resistant. Therefore research was conducted to determine if the semidwarfs' susceptibility could be altered by use of a growth substance to change the host plants' growth pattern.

Two consecutive foliar sprays of gibberellic acid (GA, 100 µg/ml) applied